

Tracking Down the Challenges Facing the Detectives and Forensic Investigators in the Public Sector of South Africa

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ABSTRACT

Investigating fraud, corruption, financial misconduct, and maladministration in the public sector of South Africa sometimes puts the lives of detectives and forensic investigators at risk. Despite the risk associated with the investigations job, detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa remain undeterred in carrying out their daily duties. From this assertion, this article aims to track down the challenges encountered by detectives and forensic investigators in South Africa's public sector. Year in and year out, the Auditor-General of South Africa reveal how billions of rands are siphoned out from state coffers across all spheres of government without services being delivered. For the past decade, service delivery in most parts of South Africa has deteriorated due to the graft of corruption, which resulted in a rise in unemployment and poverty among the people. A descriptive and qualitative research approach was followed in this study. Data presented in the study was purposively selected. The study found that forensic investigators need to be provided with tools to address the objectives of investigations and produce quality forensic investigation reports. Over and above, employers must always put protective measures in place for forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa so that they can continue to perform their investigation duties without fear and favour.

Keywords: Corruption, detectives, evidence, forensic investigators, public sector.

INTRODUCTION

Having a constructive public service culture that promotes honesty, hard work and ethical leadership, as well as detectives and forensic investigators, committed to professional ethics values and goals, is one of the best practices South Africa can employ to arrest criminals and build a culpable state. This is because the biggest threats to the corruptors and corruptees are the presence of honest and ethical public servants who do not tolerate corrupt activities and

behaviour that undermines the state and public service (Newham & Faull, 2011:51). Equally, the main threats to the South African economy and its growth is corruption and unethical leadership. Mokhomole (2023:19) cited corruption committed by public servants as contributing to the state's losses of billions of rands every year. These billions of rands aimed to deliver basic services such as roads, water and sanitation, housing, and electricity. Every year, the Auditor-General of South Africa (AGSA) reports' highlight how billions of rands go to waste due to the prevalence of corruption across the spheres of government in the public sector of South Africa. To promote honesty and a high standard of professional ethics, as indicated in section 195(1)(a) of the 1996 Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, decisive actions are required to be taken against detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa who are dishonest and participate in criminal activities. This can only be achieved when the general public or citizens are sensitised to the consequences of colluding with corrupt detectives and forensic investigators. The general public cannot be faulted for the unlawful conduct and corrupt behaviour of certain individuals (investigators) within the public sector of South Africa. The detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa, including those employed in other organs of the State, are duty-bound to independently investigate any offence without interference and influence by senior officials or political heads. In addition, Majila, Taylor and Raga (2017:95) cite a lack of political will to tackle corruption and political interference in some of the carried-out investigations, amongst other things, that contribute to lower morale and exposure to bribery to some of the detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa.

Detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector have to put their lives at risk when they investigate fraud, corruption, financial misconduct and maladministration committed by senior officials, individuals or Political Exposed Persons (PEPs) and/ or politically connected in the public sector of South Africa. Thus, these investigators need support from the state to prevent some of the risks associated with the type of work. The risk stems from when they are tasked to investigate fraud, corruption, financial misconduct, and maladministration in South Africa's public sector. Currently, measures need to be put in place to support the work of detectives and forensic investigators in South Africa's public sector. The main research question is to track down the challenges detectives and forensic investigators face when conducting investigations in South Africa's public sector. The study objective is to highlight the challenges encountered or likely to be encountered by the detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa when executing their investigation duties due to the need for more necessary support, tools and resources. The research highlights the risks associated with conducting investigation work in South Africa's public sector.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

The study adopted a descriptive and qualitative research approach. This is because these two types of research approaches are used interchangeably since the main focus is on complete, precise and reliable data (Mokhomole, Khosa & Olutola, 2023:7). Moreover, the study results produced from descriptive and qualitative research can provide practical reality of what is happening within the investigations field contrary to traditional way of having reports been

presented to the Executives, Audit Committees, Portfolio Committees in Parliament, Provincial Legislatures and Municipal Councils for decision-making purposes.

The gathering of literature review and identification of themes were purposively selected based on the study subject. Besides, purposive sampling was preferred by the researchers in this study to choose and describe data to track down the challenges facing detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa (Bakkalbasioglu, 2020:689). This is because the discussion and identifying literature and themes were selected based on their relevance to the study (Guest, Namey & Mitchell, 2013).

Moreover, the researchers used maximum variation sampling to access and select a wide range of data from online media reports, articles, and journals to track down the challenges facing detectives and forensic investigators in South Africa's public sector. This is because maximum variation sampling is the most commonly used purposive sampling design. The designs allow researchers to obtain various views to demonstrate the difficulties encountered by detectives and forensic investigators while conducting their investigations within the public sector of South Africa (Omona, 2013:179).

The researchers used Thematic and Textual Content Analysis (TCA) for data analysis. The TCA was conducted based on complete data on the challenges facing the detectives and forensic investigators in South Africa's public sector. Thematic content analysis is described as a set of analytical approaches in which systematic and objective measures are adopted to define the content of meanings using qualitative indicators that permit researchers to obtain new data from existing facts based on research guidelines and limitations. Thematic content analysis means narrating content presented into the study based on identified themes (Oliveira, Bitencourt, Teixeira & Santos, 2013:74). For this study, transcripts such as media reports (newspapers), online articles and journals were applied as sources of information for content analysis. Media reports are the leading source of information where TCA relating to detectives and investigators exposed to bribery and death threats were used to produce study results. Thematic analysis was used to identify patterns from a wide range of data collected from media reports, articles and journals (secondary data), including to discover themes that highlighted and pronounced the challenges faced by the detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa.

The flexibility of employing textual content analysis to manage data gathered from media reports, articles and journals makes this approach very influential. Content analysis can help researchers produce theory from the collected data and use theory to examine the data (Stemler, 2015:11). The data produced for textual analysis in this study is derived from articles, media reports and journals. These types of information were examined as the 'texts' in this study and used to assess the meanings of the challenges facing the detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa (Smith, 2017:1).

DISCUSSION ON IDENTIFIED THEMES AND LITERATURE REVIEW

RESEARCH BACKGROUND

The background of the study is to track down the challenges detectives and forensic investigators face when conducting investigations in South Africa's public sector. Leading to these challenges is the widespread corruption in the public sector of South Africa, which requires to be investigated by detectives and forensic investigators. However, detectives and forensic investigators can only carry out these investigation functions to the best of their ability with the state's support with necessary tools and resources, including legislative frameworks.

Every year, investigations reports containing the findings and recommendations for allegations of fraud, corruption, financial misconduct, irregularities and maladministration committed by senior officials, individuals or Political Exposed Persons (PEPs) are submitted and presented to the relevant authorities without any action being taken against the implicated persons. This was confirmed by the AGSA (2023:61) that there was a lack of appropriate action on fraud, corruption, financial misconduct, irregularities and maladministration committed by senior officials, individuals or PEPs. At the same time, the relevant authorities continued to ignore the findings and recommendations of investigators. Thus, that is a sign of a lack of state corporate governance, control measures and accountability, which impacts the outputs of the detectives and forensic investigators.

Some of the investigation reports are dismissed in the court of law or disciplinary processes due to the poor quality of the investigation to prove beyond reasonable doubt that an offence was committed. For instance, Ferreira (2023) cited the "State Capture Nulane Trial", where the judge pointed out that "it was clear that R24.9 million had flowed from the state's coffers, but regrettably, the prosecution had failed to show what happened to the money." The accused individuals in this matter were acquitted due to poor investigation by the investigating officials. Often, skills, tools and resources are cited as contributing to poor-quality investigation reports.

IDENTIFIED THEMES, REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND STUDY RESULTS

- **Uncooperative of witnesses and suspects**

Mothibi (2021) cited (Gilili, 2021) that the lack of cooperation by implicated officials in the Supply Chain Management and Finance units in the public sector of South Africa is a challenge to forensic investigators. This becomes difficult for forensic investigators to establish what happened, taking into account that forensic investigators do have powers to subpoena witnesses contrary to other law enforcement agencies such as the South African Police Service (SAPS) Directorate for Priority Crime Investigations (DPCI) which (commonly known and/ or refer to as Hawks) and the Public Protector of South Africa (PPSA).

Evidence can be acquired orally through interviews with the people of interest. In the context of South Africa, interrogations are often conducted by police against person(s) of interest, including obtaining confessions from uncooperative and hostile witnesses and/ or suspects. Section 26 of the Criminal Procedure Act, 51 of 1977 strategically gives the police the power to gain valuable

information from uncooperative witnesses or persons (s) of interest. As a result, forensic investigators must be aware of legal imperatives governing the processes of attaining information from witnesses and suspects during investigations of wrongdoing and/ or transgression (Patso, 2022:46).

Researchers expressed that detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa gather evidence by interviewing witnesses and suspects and reviewing documents relating to the matter under investigation. During these processes, forensic investigators may encounter difficulties ranging from witnesses who could be more cooperative to not telling the truth. Some witnesses may agree to be interviewed and later refuse to sign their affidavits or statements taken from them. At the same time, some of the witnesses may dispute the evidence provided to investigators, citing that they were forced to say things by the forensic investigators or tortured to confess by the detectives.

The court of law also clarified the issues of uncooperative or hostile witness(s) who tend to change their statements during the trial and disciplinary hearing. This issue of hostile witness was ventilated in the matter between Makhala & Another v The State (438/2020) [2021] ZASCA 19 (18 February 2022). The court concluded and ruled that:

'[t]he two statements made by Luzuko Makhala to the police were not unlawfully obtained, and the two statements were correctly admitted into evidence. That evidence afforded proof of the appellants' complicity in the murder of Mr Molosi and the further charges associated with his murder. There was no failing on the trial judge's part in cautioning himself against the frailties of the evidence of Luzuko Makhala as an accomplice, nor in his declaration of Luzuko Makhala as a hostile witness. The trial court correctly found sufficient evidence to corroborate the statements of Luzuko Makhala and that, upon considering all the evidence, the State had discharged its burden of proof.'

This court judgement derived from the trial court judgement whereby *'the State called Luzuko Makhala to give evidence. Without forewarning to the prosecution, Luzuko Makhala recanted the contents of his first and second statements that incriminated himself and the accused in the murder. The prosecution sought to have Luzuko Makhala declared a hostile witness. The trial court did so. Luzuko Makhala testified that the incriminating portions of the statements were fabrications that the police forced him to record in the statements. He claimed that he was intimidated by the police and threatened with assault and, as a result, made statements that he thought the police wanted from him.'*

Van Graan (2017:61-65) emphasises that forensic investigators adopted the Liverpool Interview Protocol (LIP) to gain more evidence from the witness. The LIP makes it easier for forensic investigators to attain information and apply their investigation methodology. This is because the LIP approach allows forensic investigators to ask witnesses open-ended questions, leading the way for more information to be provided by the witnesses. Moreover, the information obtained from the witnesses using the LIP becomes pragmatic to implement in the forensic report.

A government employee was arrested and detained for allegedly refusing to sign a subpoena requiring her to testify as a witness in a fraud trial. It was reported that the witness "defied the court's instructions by refusing to receive or sign for the J32 subpoena in a criminal proceeding which summonsed her to attend and give evidence in court." The arrest was commended as the first step in the right direction since it served as a reminder that witnesses must give testimony in disciplinary hearings and the court of law, not at their terms, will and/ or pleasure (TimesLive, 2022).

Perhaps an arrest of this nature can send a strong message to everyone that they must assist the employer and court in resolving a dispute, crime and transgression through their testimony.

Notwithstanding that Section 16(b)(5) of the Public Service Act of 1994 (PSA), Section 15(4)(f) and 17(5) of the Public Administration and Management Act, 11 of 2014 (PAMA) and Regulation 11(e) and 14(e) of the Public Service Regulations of 2016 (PSR) speaks about co-operation with public institutions established under the Constitution and legislation, and co-operate fully with other employees in promoting and advancing the interest of the public while performing their official duties, however, researchers hold the view that these sections are silent in relations to public servants collaborations with investigators when performing their investigations duties.

- **Lack of investigative tools and resources**

In South Africa, detectives may apply for 205 of the Criminal Procedure Act, 51 of 1977, to obtain and execute subpoenas for proper police investigation of crimes. For instance, documents such as bank statements may be obtained through subpoena from the banks of the person of interest if there are and/ or may be reasonable prospects of the movement of money in and out of the bank accounts, which may assist a police officer (detective) to expose economic severe crimes such as corruption, fraud and money laundering against their investigations.

The same sentiment was shared by the Kwazulu-Natal (KZN) High Court sitting in Durban in the matter between *Panday v Minister of Police and Others*. Paragraph 29 of the judgement stipulates that "even under the current Constitutional protection of an individual's rights to privacy and property, Section 205 remains an effective means to obtain disclosure and production of information despite the potential invasion of the rights above (see *Nel supra*) as it serves the 'legitimate state interest of investigating and prosecuting crime'."

Paragraph [6] of the judgement states that "it is common cause that Section 205(1) is a valid provision and does not offend against any constitutional right." This was clarified in the matter between ***Nel v Le Roux N O & Others 1996 (3) SA 562 (CC) at para 20*** of the judgement whereby "the Constitutional Court rejected the contention that S 205 infringed several fundamental constitutional rights and held that S 205 was 'narrowly tailored as possible to meet the legitimate state interest of investigating and prosecuting crime', and that witnesses must testify.

Forensic investigators use databases such as TransUnion, Central Supplier Database(CSD), Companies and Intellectual Property Commission (CIPC), tape records, Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) devices, and Cameras, to name a few, to verify the credibility of information provided and confirm the merit of the allegations reported. Button, Kapenda and Stiemstedt (2022:161-164) cite specialist databases such as National Hunter, data mining/matching applications such as CyberSource, cameras including covert cameras, radios, covert listening devices, tracking devices, bug detectors and drones as the most commonly used investigative tools by private, forensic and In-House (both public and private) investigators across the globe.

Mokhomole (2023:28) cites *Encase - for extracting information from a laptop, XRY - for cellphones and Nexus and Experian for background checks*, amongst others, as tools used by some forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa to identify, retrieve, preserve and analyse evidence collected and presented during the investigations.

Besides, Mumba and Venter (2014) emphasise that forensic investigators use hardware and software tools to gather and retrieve required evidence during the investigations of various offences. These authors also pointed out XRY complete package (Micro Systemation), digital video disc (DVD) (to copy evidence for multiple stakeholders such as Labour/ Employee Relations for disciplinary actions and Legal Services for civil recovery), A Laptop/ Computer (for report writing), A faraday bag (to isolate and package mobile devices) and A digital camera (for documentation of potential evidence found at the scene of crime) as tools used for mobile forensics.

In 2020, it was reported that the SAPS “stuck with expired licences for their digital forensic tools — software and hardware crucial to obtaining and analysing digital evidence from devices like smartphones, laptops and surveillance cameras”. Notwithstanding that the expired licence does not threaten the forensic and police detectives to extract evidence from electronic devices during severe criminal investigations, however, the attaining of evidence will create a gap for criminals to walk free as their attorney will use the legitimacy of the acquired evidence in their defence (Swart, 2022).

Indeed, the researchers share the same sentiments with Swart (2022) that the licence to some of the utilised outsourced forensic investigations tools by detectives and forensic investigators expires and remains unused despite being operational. Suppose detectives and forensic investigators utilise these expired tools to attain evidence. In that case, the credibility of such evidence remains questionable, including the fact that defence lawyers technically may use such obtained evidence through unlicensed or unauthorised tools against the state to free criminals from being prosecuted and sentenced.

- **Death threats**

It became common for forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa to be threatened daily when executing their mandate and duties. To ensure that forensic investigators perform their duties without fear, favour or threats, the Special Investigating Unit (SIU) puts protective measures in place on critical matters where investigators receive threats to protect their investigators (Gillili, 2021). In other words, defensive steps need to be established by employers for forensic investigators and activated if threats emerge.

Members of the DPCI (the Hawks) were also reported to be among the investigators in the public sector who also receive death threats when performing their duties, similar to forensic investigators. A man was arrested for allegedly threatening senior government officials, including “continuously stalking some members from the Hawks with threatening messages and death threats” (Pijoo, 2020). In other words, that’s how the threats can be escalated towards the investigators in South Africa’s public sector. The culprits remain adamant to the extent that they can even claim responsibility for the deaths of other investigators or witnesses.

On 31 January 2023, the Daily Maverick reported that investigating officers from SAPS are among the investigators who are gradually targeted by organised criminal groups that are the subject of investigations for various offences. This assertion derives from the arrest of 24 suspects linked to the murder of a top Detective in Western Cape Province, ‘*Lieutenant-Colonel (Lt Col) Charl Kinnear*’ in September 2021. During the course of the investigation into the death of Lt. Col. Kinnear, members of the DPCI assembled a team of investigators who began to receive life threats (death

threats), including their families (Cruywagen, 2023). This shows how far criminals can go to protect their criminal activities. If the lives of police officers who are well trained as well as equipped with protective gear such as bulletproof and handguns can be threatened, then what about the lives of ordinary forensic investigators in South Africa who have no protective gear? The brutal truth is that the lives of forensic investigators and their families remain jeopardised in South Africa.

According to (Cruywagen, 2023), the escalation of these threats reaches the point where some investigators have to move their families for safety reasons while busy with the investigation. While these threats against members of the DPCI investigating teams continued, the investigators remained resolute and committed throughout the investigation processes. The researchers are of the view that notwithstanding the danger and threats that come up with the investigation work, most of the investigators remain committed and do not give up on covering up the graft of irregularities, corruption, fraud, financial misconduct, malpractices, etc. in the public sector of South Africa, including not leaving any stone unturned.

Thus, researchers hold the view that a lack of protective intervention measures runs a risk of SAPS detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa surrendering to the threats due to fear of losing their lives and that of their family members.

- **Lack of transcripts to support investigation carried out by forensic investigators**

Failure to keep records (more especially paper trails of procurement documents) by officials in state institutions such as the Passenger Rail Agency of South Africa (PRASA), Eskom, etc. in South Africa was pointed out as a challenge and hindering some of the carried out investigations from being completed (Van Minnen, 2021). At Eskom, it was reported that essential documents linked to "multibillion-rand contracts" went missing when "an internal battle rages" between the former Eskom CEO, André de Ruyter and some of the officials "who were part of the corruption" and were subjected to investigations (Cowan, Masondo & Karim 2021).

During the SIU investigation into the affairs of PRASA, it was established that officials could have deliberately destroyed some of the critical documents for investigations to hide the pathway of corruption and irregularities within the State-Owned Entities (SOEs). Poor contract management and improper document control, as well as unavailability of crucial documents, were described by the SIU as, amongst other things, "a deliberate attempt to mislead the public, frustrate investigations, and a shielding of officials working for PRASA" (Van Minnen, 2021).

The SIU pointed out the destruction and hiding of evidence and the non-availability of documentation as a massive strain on the investigative process and the completion of the investigations. The lack of documentation and poor records management within the public sector of South Africa was further revealed as one of the challenges and limitations in the investigation process of irregularities, fraud, corruption and malpractices (Hlengwa, 2021).

The study established that even though policies are crafted in the public sector of South Africa, most of these policies have gaps and loopholes which enable some public servants to commit fraud, corruption, irregularities, malpractices and financial misconduct, resulting in the state losing billions of rands. The state institutions and government departments need to be consistent when crafting policies such as Supply Chain Management and Human Resource Management policies, which regulate the procurement processes and the conduct of public servants. These policies

need to be revised or revisited annually as part of control measures. The public, including public servants, must note that laws and regulations must be violated for one to be disciplined, arrested, dismissed and regarded as a transgressor in the public sector.

Sometimes, evidence in the form of transcripts gets destroyed or concealed by implicated officials of the departments. It becomes more difficult for forensic investigators to conclude investigations without relevant transcripts of the matter being probed.

- **Most of the investigators in the public sector of South Africa are exposed to bribery**

Being an investigator or forensic investigator in the public sector of South Africa comes with many risks. Some investigators might agree and accept gratifications in the form of money, donations, rewards, fees, gifts, etc., for themselves to act unlawfully. Cruywagen (2023) indicates that some of the investigators can go as far as colluding with criminals, stealing dockets, destroying key evidence as well as spying and spearheading investigations that lead to the assassination of their colleagues.

Some investigators go as far as defeating the ends of justice from collisions and inducements received from criminals and organised crime grouping. According to Vaalweekblad (2023), a SAPS Detective (investigator) was arrested by the DPCI Serious Corruption Investigation team after he attempted to book out a Zimbabwean national from custody. The Detective was charged with defeating the ends of justice after it was established that "he had no case connected to the accused."

A similar incident happened in 2018 whereby two SAPS Detectives from the Boksburg police station were arrested on 15 January 2020 after an investigation was initiated against them. The arrest was effected following an investigation by the Hawks Serious Corruption Investigation Unit against the two Detectives for allegedly demanding an amount of R2,000.00 as a bribe from the complainant in June 2018 in return for the complainant "not to be arrested for an alleged reckless and negligent driving." The two Detectives were charged with corruption and defeating the ends of justice (South African Police Service, 2020).

News24 (2019) reported that a senior cop working within the Family Violence, Child Protection and Sexual Offence was arrested in connection to the allegations of fraud and corruption. Amongst the allegations was that "when the accused was investigating rape and sexual assault cases, he would approach the family of suspects he was investigating and demand a bribe to drop the charges."

After the SAPS Anti-Corruption Unit arrested the said police officer, the suspect was charged with defeating the ends of justice. The charge is correlated to the statement presented to court whereby it was revealed that "the accused did wrongfully and intentionally perform the following acts: take money from an accused person and gave it to the victim's father. The case was [dropped] without the complainant's knowledge" (News24, 2019). From the researcher's point of view, this demonstrates the extent to which some of the investigators can do to obstruct or defeat the course of justice.

From the above four scenarios and narrations, it turns out to be either way around in that culprits are exposed to bribe demands from SAPS Detectives. Moreover, the SAPS detectives

(investigators) tasked with investigating such offences solicit bribes or rewards from culprits about to be arrested and charged for various offences.

In the Mpumalanga Province, a man was arrested and sentenced to four years for trying to bribe the SIU investigator. It was found that a man offered and handed over R50,000.00 gratification to the investigator to drop the case of the investigation related to Covid-19 Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) against his sister. It was further revealed that the detainee did this to protect his sister, who was a public servant, as government employees are disbarred from conducting business with the state or any organ of the state in South Africa (Nombembe, 2023).

In short, the researchers hold a strong view that during the execution of investigations of various offences, the integrity of investigators or forensic investigators will constantly be tested by those who are the subject of investigations. Sometimes, those on the wrong side of the law will do everything possible to get out of trouble. In doing so, they will put a price tag towards the investigators or forensic investigators in return for them to defeat the ends of justice or destroy the corruption case against them.

Nevertheless, to minimise the exposure to corrupt activities for detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa, Newham and Faull (2011:52) suggest that the State through its investigative oversight bodies namely the Public Service Commissioner (PSC), Independent Police Investigative Directorate (IPID) and Judge Complaints Unit (JCU) (*commonly known as the Office of the Judge*) should embark on a campaign to find, acknowledge and remunerate a hardworking and dedicated detectives, investigators and/ or forensic investigators for their delightful jobs.

Moreover, 'Integrity Certificates' and recognition for sterling work by those who reject bribes expose corruptors and corruptees amongst them and members of the public and report those who attempt to bribe them. The reward and granting of such certificates of recognition should sometimes be accompanied by promotion and transfers to motivate those who remain behind or want to pursue the investigation career (Newham & Faull, 2011:52).

- **Political interference**

The Group Forensic and Investigations Services (GFIS) was established in 2016 by the Democratic Alliance (DA)-led coalition as the City of Johannesburg (CoJ) anti-fraud and corruption-busting unit and services. In its establishment, the graft-busting unit's role and mandate was to investigate theft of the city's assets, vandalism of its infrastructure, maladministration, illegal connections, breach of security, and hijacked properties (Patrick, 2023).

The (GFIS) was then disbanded in 2023 after a political power shift. The DA-led coalition was in favour of the GFIS as part of their effort to fight the graft of corruption and malfeasance in the City as opposed to the Government of Local Unity, comprised of the African National Congress (ANC), Economic Freedom Fighters (EFF), Patriotic Alliance (PA) and minority party coalition which disbanded the GFIS unit. Koko (2023) reported that the disbanding was used as a scapegoat to evade accountability for the blow of approximately R2.2 billion on corrupt contracts by CoJ Waste Management Company called Pikitiup. This corruption was revealed in an investigations report instituted by the City of Johannesburg's graft-busting unit, GFIS.

Another published report, it was reported that the disbanded was due to the deliberations of the 13th Ordinary Sitting of Council led by the Government of Local Unity, which resolved that the "investigations conducted by the GFIS were neither compliant with the local government disciplinary regulations for senior managers, nor compliant with the approved GFIS delegations of authority" (Patrick, 2023). It was alleged that the GFIS unit abused its investigative power while executing some of its investigations. The CoJ Executive Mayor, Councillor Kabelo Gwamada, also alleged that the GFIS was abusively used by DA-led collation to harass certain senior City officials and Councillors (Patrick, 2023). There is no doubt that the involvement of two administrations in the affairs of the GFIS unit serves as the confirmation of political interference.

Smit (2019:166) admits that it is a mammoth task for detectives and forensic investigators to do their work without being interfered politically. In the absence of legislation that governs and guides the investigative duties of forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa, such a gap will always invite political manipulations and interferences over the investigations conducted. Quah (2015), as cited by Smit (2019:169), indicates that detectives and forensic investigators sometimes fail to produce investigation results or fulfil their mandate due to, amongst other things, political interference and a lack of political will to support the work of investigators, similar to whistle-blowers.

Moreover, on the eve of the disbandment of GFIS, the CoJ Council Speaker appointed a Senior Council (SC) "to conduct the required legal assessment, produce an opinion and preside over the investigation on various matters relating to GFIS." The appointment of SC emerged from the allegations that DA-led collation used the GFIS to conduct unlawful investigations into some of the council members. At the same time, the DA claims that the disbandment of GFIS intended to reverse the work done by the unit to cover up and allow the continuation of corrupt activities within the CoJ (Patrick, 2023).

In an ideal world, the operational stability of detectives and forensic investigators is often affected by political interference (Smit (2019:61). Quite often, the Forensic Investigation Units similar to the Directorate for Priority Crime Investigation (DPCI) (*commonly known as the Hawks*), Special Investigating Unit (SIU) and the Public Protector South Africa (PPSA) remain underfunded due to direct political interference in these multi-anti-corruption agencies independent operations. In the meantime, the politicians would claim to be pushing back against corruption and maleficence in South Africa's public sector through speeches.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study results recommend that forensic investigators be adequately regulated, including provided with peace officer powers similar to that of the SAPS and other law enforcement agencies. Researchers further recommend that Section 16(b)(5) of PSA, Section 15(4)(f) and 17(5) of the PAMA, and Regulation 11(e) and 14(e) of the PSR must be expanded (amended) to include the co-operations with investigators of the public sector to assist in investigations when required, whether through providing documents or participating in interviews as the current stand of this legislation are not clear in relations to the cooperation's with the investigations. Moreover, these legislations must outline the consequences for employees who fail and/ or refuse to cooperate

with investigations. Over and above forensic investigators must be empowered with the tools and necessary resources to swiftly complete investigations of fraud, corruption, maladministration, irregularities and financial misconduct in the public sector of South Africa. The National Treasury must assist in procuring services such as the MIE ZoomOut system through a 'transversal contract' to enable detectives and forensic investigators in the public sector of South Africa to easily access Home Affairs, Banks and SAQA for ID, Bank Accounts and Qualification, Verifications when conducting a comprehensive investigation. The MIE ZoomOut system will further assist detectives and forensic investigators in accessing other government systems such as Personnel and Salaries Management System (Persal), Criminal Record, CIPC Directorship, Property Transactions, Credit Checks, Treasury Non-Preferred Suppliers, the South African Revenue Service (SARS), Ownership of Properties or Properties registered under the names of individuals of interests during the investigations. Researchers also recommend that public entities begin digitalising financial transactions to leave a paper trail for future inquiries. The study recommended that an independent body be established to regulate the conduct of forensic investigators, including overseeing the performance of forensic investigation units in South Africa's public sector.

The suspects of crimes and the general public must report the extortion from both detectives and forensic investigators to the DPCI Serious Corruption Investigation Unit, SAPS Anti-Corruption Unit and PSC. While the detectives and forensic investigators must also report accused individuals and/or those subject to investigations to relevant authority or power, they may and desist from taking advantage of those who attempt to bribe them. Furthermore, the PSC, IPID, and Office of the Judge must regularly undertake a campaign to find, acknowledge, and reward dedicated detectives and forensic investigators for their sterling investigation job in South Africa's public sector. Rewarding hard work will motivate the demotivated detectives and investigators to hit the ground running to fight back against the graft of corruption in South Africa's public sector.

CONCLUSION

Detectives and forensic investigators can overcome these challenges if the unit is adequately regulated, including being provided with powers similar to those of the SAPS and other law enforcement agencies. These challenges can also be overcome when forensic Investigators in the public sector of South Africa are provided with the required tools and are expected to report their investigation results to the proper, well-established Independent Body. The reality is that detectives and forensic investigators carry out investigations. However, the critical question to be interrogated and answered by the public is the output (results) at the end of these investigations. There needs to be more political will to implement the results of forensic investigations, as some implicated individuals are politically connected. Investigations cannot be carried out for compliance; consequently, management should follow after that to support the results. Everyone found to be on the wrong side of the law must be held accountable to minimise criminalities across the spheres of government.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest at present.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR (*optional*)

Tumiso Mokhomole is the main author of the Article. Bellah Lesetja Legodi (Co-author) provided inputs based on 12 years of experience in forensic investigations and a review of the article. Gloria Lebogang Mataboge (co-author) was responsible for reviewing and adding ideas to the article as a seasoned forensic investigator.

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